

Lab-Scale Development of Polyurethane Rigid Foam Composites with Latent Heat Storage Capacity for Thermal Insulation: Insights from the ECHO Project

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This study investigates the potential of polyurethane rigid foam – phase change material (PURF-PCM) composites for thermal insulation of the Cooling Thermal Energy Storage (CTES) systems, with a focus on residential applications under the Horizon Europe ECHO project. The research addresses the pressing need for a smart functional thermal insulation composite designed for the sustainable, compact, and efficient CTES system of ECHO to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and improve energy efficiency in alignment with EU climate objectives. In the lab-scale PURF-PCM composite development, ethyl palmitate was utilized as the organic PCM component for latent heat thermal energy storage with melting onset temperature at 21.3 °C, which was incorporated at different mass fractions inside the foam matrix. Differential scanning calorimeter, thermogravimetric analyser and transient plane source thermal conductivity analyser were employed to characterize the thermophysical properties of the composites. Physical characterization was conducted via gravimetric leakage tests and optical microscope imaging. According to the differential scanning calorimetry analyses, the PURF-PCM composites comprise latent heat storage capacity up to 22.5 kJ/kg at the onset phase change temperature of the organic PCM inside the PURF matrix.

This work provides significant contributions to the understanding of direct incorporation of an organic PCM as latent heat storage medium in PURF in laboratory scale and sets the stage for the pilot scale production of PURF-PCM smart functional thermal insulation composites in practical implementation. The findings emphasize the potential of up scaling the PURF-PCM fabrication by using high-pressure polyurethane foaming machines and laying the foundation for future efforts in utilization of PURF-PCM composites in thermal insulation of full-scale CTES units for energy-efficient residential applications.

Keywords: Thermal insulation, Polyurethane foam, Thermal properties, PCM, Latent heat storage

INTRODUCTION

Primary energy sources have been dominating the world energy market and future perspectives indicate 75-80% of world's energy will be supplied by these sources by 2030 [1]. The main share of the energy consumption is related to commercial and residential buildings, which is responsible for one-third of the globe's greenhouse gas emissions [2]. However, worldwide environmental concerns and limited reserves draw attention to the necessity of reducing the consumption of the primary energy sources.

One way to reduce the energy consumption is to increase the energy efficiency by controlling the energy transfer. For example, thermal insulation plays an important role to maintain temperature stability and reduce the energy consumption related to heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) systems in building sector.

To achieve thermal insulation, polyurethane rigid foams (PURF) have been widely used in different application areas in the forms of continuous/discontinuous insulation panels, spray foam or pipe insulation foam. They offer remarkable insulation value per unit thickness with respect to different foam formulations [3].

Phase change materials (PCMs) are important tools for heat and cold deposition, which are capable of storing or releasing significant amount of heat during phase change in a small temperature range. They are divided into two main groups of inorganic and organic PCMs. The inorganics represent the largest groups of PCMs, including slat hydrates, nitrates and hydroxides. Although they are cheap and easy-to-obtain chemicals, they principally suffer from low chemical/thermal stability and corrosiveness. However, organic PCMs are more robust with reliable thermal/chemical properties. They are more suitable for encapsulation in a polymer matrix with low supercooling. Paraffin

waxes, fatty acids, sugar alcohols, fatty acid esters/diesters are the most widely covered organic PCMs in literature [4-13].

Taking the advantages of the thermal energy storage capacity of PCMs and the thermal insulation performance of PURFs, researchers paid attention to incorporate PCM into PURF to promote energy efficiency with better thermal insulation for temperature targeted specific applications. In this sense, custom made PURF-PCM composites can be fabricated for the desired temperature interval of the application, which bear additional thermal buffering property at the phase change temperature of the utilized PCM.

Literature reports indirect [14-16], direct [17,18] and post-direct [19] incorporations of PCMs into PURF. In direct incorporation, PCM is directly added into the polymerization pod of liquid polyurethane components, while initially encapsulated PCM is used in indirect incorporation. The indirect incorporation is generally preferred for PCMs which are incompatible with polyurethane and its reaction mechanism to prevent any leakage or deformation in the polymer structure [14-16]. The post-direct method represents physical adsorption of liquid PCM into readily available PU foam boards. It is mostly used for adsorption of inorganic PCMs, such as salt solutions, in open-cell polyurethane foam boards [19].

The majority of the reported studies on indirect incorporation of PCM in PURF have used microencapsulated paraffins as the core material [20].

Borreguero et al. [14] investigated the effect on the thermal and mechanical properties of PURF using different amounts of Rubitherm RT27, which is a hydrocarbon-based commercial microencapsulated PCM. They reported that continuous addition of PCM microcapsules led to a denser foam with reduced mechanical properties although enhanced thermal energy storage capacity was observed. Tinti et al. [15] studied the indirect incorporation of microencapsulated n-tetradecane in melamine-formaldehyde shell. They reported that the optimum mass fraction of microencapsulated PCM is 13.5 wt.% while higher mass fraction of microencapsulated PCM resulted in a high viscosity liquid mixture that gave poor quality PURF-PCM composites.

Unlike the studies reporting the indirect incorporation of PCMs, there are only a few numbers of studies available in literature for direct incorporation of PCMs in PURF.

Aydın and Okutan [17] investigated the direct incorporation of a fatty acid ester PCM (myristyl myristate) in PURF, which has melting temperature at around 40°C. They stated that the direct incorporation of PCM into PURF provided higher total heat absorption capacity of the foam. According to their reported data, up to 22.6 wt.% PCM enabled 45.69 kJ/kg latent heat storage capacity and around 34 % total heat absorption capacity enhancement compared to the neat PURF. Sarier [18] incorporated n-hexadecane and n-octadecane into PURF applying different mass ratios. They reported that some leakage was observed due to the relatively small size of the molecules. They observed up to 77.8 kJ/kg melting enthalpy in the presence of n-octadecane with a mass ratio of 1:1.4 (PCM:PURF). However, both studies are lack of reporting the effect of the high PCM content inside the PURF matrix on thermal conductivity of the final product.

Based on the observed limited number of available papers for direct incorporation of PCMs in PURF matrix and the missing data on bringing thermal conductivity and latent heat storage issues together, the aim of this study is to investigate the feasibility of direct incorporation of a fatty acid ester-based PCM into PURF at different mass ratios in lab-scale and to demonstrate its compatibility with the polymer matrix for development of smart functional thermal insulation composites. The reported lab-scale data provide valuable fundamental information for pilot-scale production of PURF-PCM thermal insulation composites, developed for specific application temperature of the CTES systems under the Horizon Europe ECHO project (Efficient Compact Modular Thermal Energy Storage System, Project No. 101096368).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

As part of the Horizon Europe ECHO project studies, PURF-PCM composites were fabricated by using industrial raw materials for further scale-up of the lab-scale investigations. The raw materials of PURF were kindly provided by Ideakim Global, Türkiye (project partner). The details of the supplied raw materials are given below.

Polymeric diphenylmethane diisocyanate (PMDI), Suprasec 5025, is the product of Hunstman with isocyanate value (NCO) of 31% and density of 1.23 g/cm³ at 25 °C. It consists of approximately 50% pure MDI, 30% tri-isocyanate, 10% tetra-isocyanate, 5% pentaisocyanate and 5% higher homologue. The average functionality of this

standard polymeric MDI is about 2.7 with a typical viscosity of 200 mPa s at 25 °C, approximately.

The sucrose-based polyether polyol, NJ-8238, is the product of Jurong Nigwu with 380 ± 15 mg KOH/g. The average functionality of the polyether polyol is 5-6 and its viscosity is 11250 ± 1250 mPa.s at 25 °C, respectively.

The other polyether polyol, Petol 400-3, is the product of Oltchim with hydroxyl value of 360-410 mg KOH/g. The average functionality of the polyether polyol is 3 and its molecular weight and density are 420 a.u and 1.05 g/cm³ at 25 °C, respectively.

N,N-Dimethylcyclohexylamine (DMCHA), Hunstman, is a widely used amine-based catalyst for a broad range of rigid and semirigid urethane foams.

The ternary amine catalyst, Polycat 41 from Evonik, is used in a wide variety of polyurethane foam for improved curing.

Silicon additive, Vorasurf DC193 from Dow Chemicals, is a general-purpose silicone surfactant for rigid polyurethane foam applications.

Tris(chloropropyl) phosphate (TCPP) and cyclopentane were used as flame retardant blowing agent in the formulations, respectively.

Ethyl palmitate, Sigma-Aldrich, was used as the organic PCM in the PURF-PCM composites.

1. Synthesis of PURF-PCM composites

Initially, the premix (A) containing polyether polyols, catalysts, silicon and flame retardant at specified amount in Table 1 was prepared and vigorously mixed by using a bench-top overhead stirrer. Then, the organic PCM was added at corresponding amounts to 5 wt.%, 10 wt.% and 15 wt% and stirred to obtain a homogeneous mixture. Afterwards, the weighted amount of PMDI (B) was added. The final mixture of A+B was stirred for an additional 5-10 s and left for free-rise of the PURF-PCM composite. The neat PURF formulation is given in Table 1.

Table 1. The neat PURF formulation

Raw Material	wt. %
NJ-8238	50.9
Petol 400-3	20
DMCHA	0.3
Polycat 41	0.3
Vorasurf DC193	2
TCPP	19
Cyclopentane	5.6
Water	1.9
PMDI	130

2. Physical characterization of PURF-PCM composites

The stability of the PCM in the foam matrix is an important parameter due to direct employment of the PCM. Therefore, leakage behaviour of the PCM in liquid state was determined gravimetrically after thermal treatment of the PURF-PCM composite samples at 55 °C for 3h. The test was successively conducted three-times for the same composite sample to clarify the stability of the entrapped PCM in liquid state clearly.

Zeiss Stemi 508 optical microscope with Axiocam 208 color camera was used to observe the cell structure of the foam samples and to determine the homogenous distribution of the directly incorporated PCM inside the foam matrix.

3. Thermal characterization of PURF-PCM composites

TA Instruments Q2000 DSC was used for the calorimetric analyses of the PCM and PURF-PCM composites under inert N₂ atmosphere at 50 mL/min flow rate. All the DSC analyses were conducted at 10 °C/min rate with 1 min isothermal at the start and end of the steps. For accuracy of the enthalpy calculations, 5-digid analytical balance was used to measure the sample weight in DSC pans and daily calibrations were conducted via indium standard. Each presented DSC data in this paper was calculated according to the results of at least four individual analyses in order to minimize uncertainty.

Thermal conductivity of the PURF-PCM composites were determined at 20 °C and 30 °C ambient temperature by using a hot disk instrument, model TPS2500S, employing the transient plane source method (TPS). The declared instrument accuracy is better than 5 %. To verify this value, preliminary tests were conducted using the reference material supplied by the manufacturer, yielding a maximum average deviation of 4.1 %. In order to provide the most accurate data, the average of eight successive analyses has been reported for each sample.

Thermogravimetric analyses were conducted by using TA Instruments Discovery TGA55 instrument for determination of the decomposition properties at elevated temperatures. The TGA runs were between 30 and 815 °C at 10 °C/min heating rate under 60 mL/min N₂ flow.

While samples for DSC analyses were collected from 4 cm and 14 cm levels in order to observe homogeneous distribution of PCM during foaming in vertical axis, samples taken from 7 cm and 14 cm levels were used for thermal conductivity and

thermogravimetric analyses, respectively. For optical microscope imaging, thin sliced samples from 14 cm level were used. The sampling levels are given in Fig.1.

Fig.1. Sampling points in foam samples

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Synthesis of PURF-PCM composites and physical evaluation of the foaming behaviour

PURF fabrication is a simple exothermic process, which takes place spontaneously between polyol and polymeric isocyanate constituents in the presence of catalyst and blowing agents. However, foaming can be interrupted when exothermic behaviour is disturbed by a thermally active agent, such as a PCM, in the reaction medium. Therefore, decrease in foam rise and deteriorations in closed cell structures are usually observed in such cases.

As it is seen in Fig.2, the synthesized PURF-PCM composites have decreasing foam lengths with the increase in PCM wt.%. The difference is more significant compared to the neat PURF sample (b), i.e., differences in cell structures of the foam matrices with potential effect on thermal conductivity of the final product. In this sense, fabrication of the neat PURF and the PURF-PCM composite with 15 wt.% have been modified by higher amount of blowing agent (x2) to support cell formation and observe its effect on thermal conductivity.

Fig.2. (a) Neat PURF with x2 blowing agent, (b) Neat PURF, (c) PURF-PCM with 5 wt.%, (d) PURF-PCM with

10 wt.%, (e) PURF-PCM with 15 wt.%, (f) PURF-PCM with 15 wt.% and x2 blowing agent

The leakage tests of the PURF-PCM composites indicate that the change in foam sample weight is less than 0.5 % in all samples after treatment at 55 °C for 3 h, which is a clear indication of stability for the directly incorporated PCM inside the foam matrix. The results of the successively conducted triplicate analysis prove the effective entrapment of ethyl palmitate in the comb like structure of the foam.

The optical microscope images, given in Fig.3, have clear signs of the changes in cell structures with increasing amount of ethyl palmitate. As it is seen in Fig.2(a,b), the neat PURFs have small cell diameters, which are mostly closed cells. The foam matrices are mostly governed by formation of many small cells during blowing without any intervention in the exothermic reaction. Similarly, 5 wt.% ethyl palmitate addition does not severely affect the cell distribution. However, significant increase in cell diameters and open cells are clearly observed for samples containing 10 and 15 wt.% ethyl palmitate in Fig.3(d,e) although it cannot be avoided with increased amount of the blowing agent in Fig.3(f). On the other hand, the consistency of the white opaque colour inside comb like structure proves the homogenous distribution of the ethyl palmitate in horizontal axis during foam formation.

Fig.3. Optical microscope images: (a) Neat PURF, (b) Neat PURF with x2 blowing agent, (c) PURF-PCM with 5 wt.%, (d) PURF-PCM with 10 wt.%, (e) PURF-PCM with 15 wt.%, (f) PURF-PCM with 15 wt.% and x2 blowing agent

2. Thermal properties of the PURF-PCM composites

The DSC analyses indicate that even small amount of PCM inside the foam matrix has a latent heat thermal energy storage contribution in the composite (Table 2). The given DSC thermograms in Fig.4 and 5 indicate that the phase change behaviour of ethyl palmitate is preserved inside the foam matrix and it does not undergo any chemical changes during foam formation. Besides, the similarity of the melting onset temperatures also supports the compatibility of the PCM. However, the intensity of the latent heat storage capacity is not directly proportional to the amount of the PCM (ethyl palmitate) wt.% due to thermal insulation effect of the PURF, which inhibits the heat transfer of the thermal agent. Similar inhibiting effect is also seen during the freezing cycles, which exhibit lower freezing onset temperatures due to polymer barrier around the PCM content with the surrounding.

According to the DSC data, thermal energy storage capacity of ethyl palmitate can be accommodated in PURF up to 22.5 kJ/kg while providing it at around 19 °C melting onset temperature.

Table 2. Latent heat storage capacity of the PURF-PCM composites and ethyl palmitate (PCM)

PCM wt.%	Heat of Fusion kJ/kg	Onset Temperature °C	Heat of Freezing kJ/kg	Onset Temperature °C
5	3.08	20.99	- 3.00	9.47
10	9.69	20.34	- 10.98	10.96
15	22.44	18.84	- 22.88	9.09
15-x2	22.18	18.86	- 22.47	8.24
PCM	182.0	21.36	- 177.1	19.19

Fig.4. DSC thermogram of ethyl palmitate

Fig.5. DSC thermograms of (a) PURF-PCM with 5 wt.%, (b) PURF-PCM with 10 wt.%, (c) PURF-PCM with 15 wt.%, (d) PURF-PCM with 15 wt.% and x2 blowing agent

Thermal insulation property of PURF is a function of its thermal conductivity, provided by the closed-cell structure in the matrix. The homogeneously distributed tiny voids of the closed-cells allow slower heat transfer rate and create a thermal buffer as a result of favoured convection compared to conduction. However, contribution of an additive might disturb closed-cell formation, cell diameters and enhance the conduction type heat transfer. Therefore, creating a suitable PURF-PCM composite as a smart functional material for practical implementation is a decision-making process by evaluating the DSC and thermal conductivity data of the samples together.

Thermal conductivity of the fabricated PURF-PCM composites and the neat PURF has been examined at 20 and 30 °C (Table 3). The neat PURF, synthesized according to the given formulation in Table 1, has thermal conductivity of 0.0351 and 0.0362 W/m.K at 20 and 30 °C, respectively. Its thermal conductivity decreases to 0.0330 and 0.0343 W/m.K with twofold increase of the blowing agent amount at 20 and 30 °C, respectively.

Table 3. Thermal conductivity of the PURF-PCM composites and neat PURF

PCM wt.%	20 °C W/m.K	30 °C W/m.K	% Increase	
5	0.0363	0.0374	3.41	3.31
10	0.0394	0.0400	12.25	10.49
15	0.0428	0.0432	21.93	19.33
15-x2	0.0423	0.0425	28.18	23.90
PURF	0.0351	0.0362	-	-
PURF-x2	0.0330	0.0343	-	-

The effect of the PCM content is directly seen in Table 3. As the PCM wt.% inside the foam matrix increases, the thermal conductivity of the composite increases. However, a drastic increase is observed for the composites containing 15 wt.% PCM, which indicates detonation of the closed-cells and governed heat transfer mechanism by conductivity together with the vast amount of PCM in the polymer

network. It is also in good accordance with the given optical microscope images in Fig.3.

For the PURF-PCM composites with 5 and 10 wt.% PCM, they present thermal conductivity values close to expanded polystyrene (EPS) foam, which is also widely used in different thermal applications in industry. Since the thermal conductivity of EPS with density 20 kg/m^3 is $0.035 - 0.037 \text{ W/m.K}$ at 10°C [21], the PURF-PCM composites with 5 and 10 wt.% PCM offer suitable thermal insulation function.

Bringing the joint effect of thermal insulation and latent heat storage, the DSC and thermal conductivity data point that PURF-PCM smart functional thermal insulation composites can be fabricated up to 10 wt.% PCM content to obtain around 10 kJ/kg of latent heat storage as a thermal buffer at the melting onset temperature (20°C) of the PCM for the CTES systems under the Horizon Europe ECHO Project.

The thermal decomposition data given in Fig.6 indicate that the PURF-PCM composites have similar thermal decomposition steps with slight differences. While PURF-PCM composites with 5 and 10 wt.% PCM show patterns similar to the neat PURF samples below 300°C , the thermal decomposition of the 15 wt.% PCM containing samples are driven by the initial decomposition of the PCM, i.e., higher weight loss at 300°C . Later, the neat PURF samples show slower decomposition rate in Fig.6 (a,b) and comprise a higher ash content at 800°C . According to the TGA data, it can be readily stated that all samples are thermally stable up to 100°C without any significant weight loss.

Fig.6. TGA curves of (a) Neat PURF, (b) Neat PURF with x2 blowing agent, (c) PURF-PCM with 5 wt.%, (d) PURF-PCM with 10 wt.%, (e) PURF-PCM with 15 wt.%, (f) PURF-PCM with 15 wt.% and x2 blowing agent

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the conducted study for development of smart functional thermal insulation materials by bringing together the thermal insulation and latent heat storage properties of PURF and PCM, the reported data significantly indicate the feasibility of PURF-PCM composites for practical implementations. The lab-scale data clearly set the limitations for direct incorporation of the PCM with regard to DSC and thermal conductivity analyses and optical microscope imaging.

Although PCM is effectively encapsulated in the polymer matrix without any leakage, structural deformations of closed-cell content of the foam cause significant increase in thermal conductivity and break down the thermal insulation function of PURF-PCM composites with 15 wt.% PCM.

This work represents a significant contribution to the field by not only advancing the understanding of development of smart functional thermal insulation composites with latent heat storage and thermal buffering property but also allowing integration of these insights into pilot scale production by using high-pressure polyurethane foaming machines in the next step for targeted practical implementations.

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